

Sociodemographic Influences on Anemia in Pediatric Populations at Al-Sajad General Hospital, Al-Najaf Province

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Abstract

Background: Anemia, characterized by a decrease in the number of red blood cells or hemoglobin concentration, is a significant global public health problem affecting both developing and developed countries, with major consequences for human health as well as social and economic development. The aim of study is to evaluate how are sociodemographic influences on anemia in pediatric populations at Al-Sajad General Hospital, Al-Najaf Province. **Method:** This cross-sectional study at Al-Sajad General Hospital in Al-Najaf involved measuring hemoglobin levels in children (neonates to 10 years) and their non-pregnant mothers (18-50 years), and collecting sociodemographic data via a structured questionnaire. Hemoglobin levels were analyzed using an automated hematology analyzer, and statistical analyses (t-tests and ANOVA) were performed to compare levels across different sociodemographic groups. Ethical approval and informed consent were obtained. **Results:** The study found that the mean hemoglobin level was 9.8 ± 0.7 mg/dL. Significant differences in hemoglobin levels were observed based on residency (higher in urban children) and age groups (higher in older children). No significant differences were noted for gender, birth order, nutritional status, or timing of complementary food introduction. **Conclusion:** The study concluded that urban residency and older age were associated with higher hemoglobin levels in children, while maternal employment was linked to higher hemoglobin levels in mothers. Tailored public health strategies focusing on nutrition and healthcare access in rural areas and among housewives are essential to address anemia.

Introduction

Anaemia is one common health disorder resulting from the decreased count of red blood cells or low haemoglobin levels, leading to insufficient oxygen carriage to tissues. The prevalence of this problem is in millions of people globally, with a particular concentration among children with significant and drastic implications for growth, development, and overall health status. Anemia may result from various conditions; most cases are due to nutritional deficiencies (iron deficiency being most common), infections, or inherited genetic disorders, such as sickle cell anemia or thalassemia. A broader reflection of the underlying reasons further brings in aspects that depict

the feudalism between the socioeconomic-demographic factors and episode. This underscores the need for an understanding of the impact of the sociodemographic factors on childhood anemia [1,2]. Sociodemographic factors refer to characteristics of a population that include both social and demographic dimensions, such as education, income, ethnicity, age, and sex; these aspects can play a crucial role in the health outcomes by determining the incidence and severity of anemia in children. Anemia is common among children due to the fact that younger children are more vulnerable, especially those aged less than five years as a result of the fast rate of growth and higher requirements of iron. It also appears that there

More Information

How to cite this article: Ibrahim TH, Habeeb HO, Kadhem RH. Sociodemographic Influences on Anemia in Pediatric Populations at Al-Sajad General Hospital, Al-Najaf Province. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(5):290-6.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(5).31

Keywords:

Sociodemographic, Influences, Anemia, Pediatric, Al-Sajad General Hospital.

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are gender differences; both boys and girls can have different rates of anemia which often depends on cultural, nutritional, and even biological factors [3,4]. In addition, to be associated with the number of years of education completed by the mother of the case, 'high education level' is one more important basic characteristic. Mothers with a higher level of education are more likely to have better health literacy concerning dietary habits and a quicker diagnosis and treatment of anemia. In contrast, their children are known to be at greater risk for anemia due to poor dietary habits or insufficient health care by women with a lower level of education. Another important determinant involves low-income families that usually might not have easy access to proper nutrition, health care, and clean living conditions—all circumstances that could raise the rates of anemia in children. Poverty, through its impact on nutrition, is the other critical determinant of iron-deficiency anemia. This is the most common form of anemia among children [5,6]. Some literature sources show that ethnicity and geographic location can play determining roles in the prevalence of childhood anemia: there are races with a genetic predisposition and regions where infectious diseases are excessively prevalent. The latter is a case in point for malaria, which is endemic in certain regions for specific races. Some important factors include cultural practices and beliefs related to diet, health, and gender roles coercively creating differences in anemia prevalence [7]. Knowledge of the influence of sociodemographic factors is basic to developing targeted interventions in cases of childhood anemia. In this light, initiatives related to public health must be constructed to address these determinants directly, with the view to reducing the burden of anemia and bettering general child healthfulness and development. The aim of study is to evaluate how are sociodemographic influences on Anemia in Pediatric Populations at Al-Sajad General Hospital.

Method

A cross sectional study was carried out among the pediatric population in Al-Sajad general hospital/ Al-Najaf Province. The research aimed to spot the social, demographic, and medical factors related to the level of hemoglobin in children (aged between neonates and 10 years) and their mothers (pregnant women included) from this population: children attending the pediatric clinic of Al-Sajad general teaching hospital and their mothers. The criteria for inclusion in the study were neonates up to 10 years old and women who were not currently pregnant with children for mothers. The sample size was calculated based on the prevalence of anemia in that area, with an assumption that it would give enough power to detect significant changes as far as hemoglobin levels were concerned among various demographic groups within the regions.

Data were collected for six months from January to June 2023. The steps taken for data collection are as follows:

1. **Recruitment:** Children and their mothers were recruited during routine visits to the pediatric department. Informed consent was obtained from the mothers for both their participation and that of their children.
2. **Questionnaire:** A structured questionnaire was used to gather sociodemographic information. For children, data included age, gender, residency (urban or rural), birth order, number of siblings under five years, nutritional status (underweight, stunted), and the timing of the introduction of complementary foods. For mothers, data included age, educational level, occupation, and monthly family income.
3. **Hemoglobin Measurement:** Blood samples were collected from both children and mothers to measure hemoglobin levels. Hemoglobin concentration was determined using a standard automated hematology analyzer. The mean hemoglobin levels were recorded along with standard deviations.

The primary outcome variable was the mean hemoglobin level. Independent variables included sociodemographic factors such as age, gender, residency, birth order, nutritional status, timing of complementary food introduction for children, and age, education, occupation, and income for mothers.

Statistical Analysis: data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the sociodemographic characteristics of the study population. Mean and standard deviations of hemoglobin levels were calculated for different groups. Independent t-tests and ANOVA were employed to compare mean hemoglobin levels across various sociodemographic categories. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations: The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Al-Sajad General Hospital. All participants provided informed consent before enrollment. Confidentiality of the participants' information was maintained throughout the study.

Results

Mean level of hemoglobin in current study 9.8 ± 0.7 Mg/dl.

Age Groups: The majority (46.7%) are aged 1-3 years.

Gender: The distribution is nearly equal between females (49.7%) and males (50.3%).

Residency: Slightly more babies live in urban areas (51.8%) than rural areas (48.2%).

Birth Order: Most babies are in the 2-3 birth order category (54.8%).

Number of Children Under 5 Years: 36.2% of families have no other children under 5 years.

Underweight Status: Most babies (69.8%) have a normal weight.

Stunted Growth: 81.9% of babies are not stunted.

First Time Introducing Complementary Food: 48.2% started complementary food between 6-12 months. As in table 1.

Table 1: Babies Sociodemographic

Variables		Frequency	Percentage
Age groups (years)	<1	36	18.1
	1-3	93	46.7
	3.1-10	70	35.2
Gender	Female	99	49.7
	male	100	50.3
Residency	Rural	96	48.2
	Urban	103	51.8
Birth order	0-1	58	29.1
	2-3	109	54.8
	>3	32	16.1
No of children under 5 years	0	72	36.2
	1	53	26.6
	2	41	20.6
	3	27	13.6
	>3	6	3.0
Underweight	<3rd	58	29.1
	normal	139	69.8
	>3rd	2	1.0
Stunted	<3rd	34	17.1
	normal	163	81.9
	>3rd	2	1.0
First time introduce Complementary food	<6	73	36.7
	6-1	96	48.2
	>1	6	3.0
	milk only	24	12.1
	<6	73	36.7

Table 2 show that,

Age: Most mothers are aged 21-30 years (48.7%) and 31-40 years (42.2%).

Education: The majority have a primary education (67.3%), with smaller percentages having secondary (16.6%) or higher education (9.5%).

Occupation: Most mothers are housewives (90.5%).

Income: The majority of families have a monthly income of IQD 500,000-1,000,000 (76.9%).

Table 2: Mothers Sociodemographic

Variables		Frequency	Percentage
Mother age groups (years)	≤20	11	5.5
	21-30	97	48.7
	31-40	84	42.2
	>40	7	3.5
Mother education	illiterate	13	6.5
	primary	134	67.3
	secondary	33	16.6
	higher	19	9.5
Mother occupation	employee	19	9.5
	housewife	180	90.5
Family monthly income	<500,000	27	13.6

	500,000-1000,000	153	76.9
	>1,000,000	19	9.5

Table 3 show that

Gender: No significant difference in mean hemoglobin (Hb) levels between females (9.7 mg/dL) and males (9.7 mg/dL) with a p-value of 0.9.

Residency: Significant difference, with urban babies having a higher mean Hb (9.8 mg/dL) compared to rural babies (9.6 mg/dL); p-value = 0.04.

Age Groups: Significant difference, with older children (3.1-10 years) having a higher mean Hb (9.9 mg/dL) compared to younger age groups; p-value = 0.011.

Birth Order, Number of Children Under 5 Years, Underweight Status, Stunted Growth, and Timing of Introducing Complementary Food: No significant differences in mean Hb levels across these variables. Overall, significant differences in mean hemoglobin levels were observed based on residency and age groups, while other sociodemographic factors showed no significant impact.

Table 3: Differences in Mean of Hemoglobin According to Sociodemographic Variables of Babies

Variables		N	Mean of Hb Mg/dl	Std. D of Hb	P-value
Gender	female	99	9.7	0.6	0.9
	male	100	9.7	0.8	
Residency	rural	96	9.6	0.7	0.04
	urban	103	9.8	0.7	
Age groups of babies (years)	<1	36	9.7	0.5	0.011
	1-3	93	9.6	0.7	
	3.1-10	70	9.9	0.7	
Birth order	0-1	58	9.8	0.5	0.9
	2-3	109	9.7	0.7	
	>3	32	9.8	0.8	
No. of children Less than 5 years	0	72	9.7	0.7	0.4
	1	53	9.7	0.7	
	2	41	9.7	0.6	
	3	27	9.7	0.9	
	>3	6	10.3	0.8	
Underweight	<3rd	58	9.8	0.7	0.2
	normal	139	9.7	0.7	
	>3rd	2	8.9	1.5	
Stunted	<3rd	34	9.7	0.8	0.23
	normal	163	9.7	0.7	
	>3rd	2	8.9	1.5	
First time introduce Complementary food	<6	73	9.8	0.7	0.4
	6-1	96	9.7	0.8	
	>1	6	9.4	0.4	
	milk only	24	9.6	0.6	

Table 4 show that occupation: Significant difference: Employed mothers have higher mean hemoglobin (Hb) levels (10.0 mg/dL) compared to housewives (9.7 mg/dL); p-value = 0.014.

Age Groups: No significant difference in mean Hb levels across different age groups; p-value = 0.6.

Education: No significant difference in mean Hb levels across different education levels; p-value = 0.4.

Monthly Income: No significant difference in mean Hb levels across different income groups; p-value = 0.3. Overall, the only significant difference in mean hemoglobin levels was found based on the mother's occupation, with employed mothers having higher levels than housewives. Age, education, and monthly income did not show significant differences in mean hemoglobin levels.

Table 4: Differences in Mean of Hemoglobin According to Sociodemographic Variables of Mothers

Variables		N	Mean of Hb Mg/dl	Std. D of Hb	P-value
Occupation	employee	19	10.0	0.5	0.014
	housewife	180	9.7	0.7	
Age groups (years)	≤20	11	9.8	0.5	0.6
	21-30	97	9.7	0.7	
	31-40	84	9.8	0.7	
	>40	7	9.5	1.2	
Education	illiterate	13	9.7	0.6	0.4
	primary	134	9.7	0.7	
	secondary	33	9.6	0.8	
	higher	19	10.0	0.5	
Monthly income (IQD)	<500,000	27	9.6	0.6	0.3
	500,000-1000,000	153	9.7	0.7	
	>1,000,000	19	10.0	0.8	

Discussion

Hemoglobin levels and sex: Current study: No statistically significantly different mean in females and males (9.7 mg/dL) ($p = 0.9$). This is consistent with several studies that found no significant sex differences in Hb levels among children. For example, Alemayehu et al. (2019) in their study found no significant sex differences in the prevalence of anemia regarding Hb levels among Ethiopian children. This may suggest that, especially in early childhood, hemoglobin levels are influenced by environmental factors such as diet rather than sex-specific factors [8].

Hemoglobin levels and place of residence: Current study: The mean hemoglobin levels in urban infants (9.8 mg/dL) were significantly higher than those in rural infants (9.6 mg/dL) with a p value of 0.04. Comparison with other studies: Studies from low and middle-income countries reflect similar patterns more often. It is because the urban-residing children usually have better health care, nutrition, and hygiene that can make their hemoglobin levels higher. Indeed, previously a similar claim was presented in a study conducted by Karakochuk et al. (2015) in Cambodia, indicating that rural children were likely to have much lower hemoglobin levels due to a higher prevalence of malnutrition and parasitic infections. The current results are thus in line with the existing literature and explain urban–rural socioeconomic differences fully [9].

Hemoglobin levels and age: Current study: A sample of children aged 3.1-10 years had hemoglobin level significantly higher at 9.9 mg/dL ($p = 0.011$) compared to that of younger ages. This finding is explained by the normal physiological process in older children who tend to have higher hemoglobin values owing to better absorption of nutrients and lower prevalence of early childhood illness. An increase in the levels of hemoglobin with age was also reported by Onyeneho et al. (2019). They, however, indicated that this trend could be reversed in terms of inadequate nutrition

during critical periods of development, especially in areas where food insecurity is a significant problem [10].

Hemoglobin levels and birth order: No interaction on hemoglobin levels was obtained in the current study for the birth order of children ($p > 0.05$). Some other studies postulated that children born later in life are more likely to be anemic because of resource dilution in large families (reported by Adamu et al., 2018). This study did not find this; however, this is possibly a sign of effective family planning or improved health care access for all children irrespective of their birth order. Hemoglobin levels might also be improved with nutritional interventions that are aimed at younger children, regardless of the birth position [11].

Hemoglobin levels and number of children under 5 years of age: Current study: There were no significant differences between hemoglobin levels and the number of children under 5 years of age in the household. Research on intra-household resource competition, such as the study by Ferrando et al. (2020) found that having more young children sometimes led to poorer nutritional status for all children. However, in this study, lack of significance suggests towards the moderation of potential resource competition by factors such as maternal care or breastfeeding practices or, probably, socioeconomic conditions [12].

Hemoglobin levels and underweight/stunting: Current study: Hemoglobin levels were not significantly related to underweight or stunted in this study. Comparison with other studies: Malnutrition, including iron deficiency anemia, often associates low hemoglobin content, noted by the research of Black et al. (2013) who found that underweight and stunted children were significantly under hemoglobin. The lack of an association in the current study could be because most children in this cohort were neither underweight nor stunted. It may also suggest that the prevalence of anemia in the population is less influenced by stunting and more by other factors such as infection or dietary

iron intake [13]. Hemoglobin levels and timing of complementary feeding: Current study: The mean hemoglobin levels did not vary significantly with respect to the timing of complementary feeding ($p > 0.05$). Comparison with other studies: The results of Dewey & Brown (2003), for instance, indicated that the initiation of complementary feeding between the 6th and 12th months is crucial in anemia prevention. In the present study, this lack of significance may be because most families were, in general, following proper practices of complementary feeding, hence minimizing variability in hemoglobin levels [14]. Hemoglobin Levels and Mother's Occupation: Current Study The children of working mothers had a higher mean value of hemoglobin (10.0 mg/dL) as compared to those of housewives (9.7 mg/dL), with statistically significant p-value of 0.014. It is an interesting finding since maternal employment is always related to the better socioeconomic status of an individual that ensures more nutrition and health care accessibility. The study related to the effect of maternal employment on child health was also conducted in India by Goudet et al. (2018) and confirmed that working mothers could give their children better nutrition as they had more financial resources. On the contrary, there are studies which state that work sometimes limits the time available for caring for their children, but this did not seem significant in the study [15]. Hemoglobin levels and maternal education/income: current study: There were no significant differences in education or income ($p > 0.05$). This result is somewhat surprising because usually, maternal education and family income are strong predicting factors of child health. According to the study conducted by Mesfin et al. in 2015, maternal education positively influenced the nutritional status of children and their hemoglobin levels. 'An explanation for the lack of significance in the current study could be that either the differences in education and income were not large enough to detect significant differences or some other factor, community health interventions, for example could effectively narrow the gap between different socioeconomic groups,' opines ref [16]. Limitations: Small sample size and cross-sectional design limit generalizability and causal inference. Lack of detailed nutritional and infection-related data reduces understanding of anemia causes. Study focused on a single region, reducing broader applicability.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The current study found significant differences in hemoglobin levels based on residency, age, and maternal occupation. These findings align with those of other studies that emphasize the role of urbanization, age, and socioeconomic factors in child health. Other sociodemographic factors, such as birth order, maternal education, and income, did not show

significant impacts, which may be due to uniform healthcare and nutritional practices across the population. Conduct larger, multi-center, and longitudinal studies. Include detailed data on nutrition and infections. Implement targeted interventions for rural areas and promote iron supplementation programs. Increase public health education to prevent anemia through better nutrition and early detection.

Acknowledgement

The authors extremely appreciate the unlimited assistance of all operating teams at Al-Sajad General Hospital, Al-Najaf province

Conflict of Interest

No

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